

A NOTE ON THE SOLUBILITY OF HYDRATED COPPER OXIDE IN NITRIC ACID

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The value of solubility product of copper oxide, as calculated by Feitknecht (*Chem. Abs.*, 1945, 856) is 1×10^{-20} . The above author has calculated it from thermal data, whereas Näsänen and Tamminen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1994) have determined it from a system of cupric oxide, cupric perchlorate and sodium perchlorate, and found the value as 2.2×10^{-20} and they claim that the cupric oxide is stable. Herein a simpler method has been adopted by the present authors.

Copper oxide, prepared from cupric chloride and caustic soda, was washed free of alkali and chloride, and dried over an electrically controlled air-oven at 110° - 115° for 15 hours. The oxide was found to contain about 5% water.

A stock solution of nitric acid, standardised against borax, was kept for preparation of other solutions by dilution.

Dilute nitric acid of known strength was shaken with sufficient copper oxide for 8 days (6 days required for equilibrium). The undissolved copper oxide was removed by filtration in a G₄ glass sintered crucible under pressure. The p_H of the filtrate was measured with a Marconi- p_H meter, and its copper content was estimated iodimetrically. The solid phase got hydrated to copper oxide of about 35% water content. This hydration did not materially affect the concentration of acid. The experiments were carried out in triplicates at room temperature (25° - 28°). A few sets of bottles were placed in a thermostat at 35° , but it was found that p_H or copper concentration did not change appreciably with temperature, proving the temperature coefficient to be small. The experimental results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Initial conc. of HNO ₃	Conc. of Cu.	p_H	$a^{\circ}Cu \times 10^{18}$	$a^{\circ}OH \times a^{Cu} \times 10^{26}$
0.0201 M	0.0100 M	5.28	37.03	1.9
0.0402	0.0200	5.20	25.63	2.3
0.0604	0.0301	5.11	16.92	1.9
0.0805	0.0384	5.02	11.19	1.5
0.1006	0.0482	4.95	8.102	1.6
0.1207	0.0580	4.84	4.882	0.8
0.1408	0.0676	4.74	3.080	0.6

Mean value: 1.5×10^{-20} .

The total concentration of copper ($[Cu]$) in the solution can be represented as :

$$[Cu] = [Cu^{2+}] + [CuO] + [Cu(NO_3)_2]$$

where $[Cu^{2+}]$, $[CuO]$ and $[Cu(NO_3)_2]$ represent the copper ion concentration, copper oxide concentration and undissociated copper nitrate concentration respectively. The

solubility of copper oxide has been reported by McDowell and Johnston (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58** 2009) as 3×10^{-3} mole of copper oxide per litre and so can be neglected. The work of Sidgwick and Tizzard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 187) on colour and concentration of copper salts leads to the complete dissociation of copper nitrate within this range of concentration. So it becomes evident that copper remaining in these two forms is not of any importance, and the total copper can be assumed to exist as Cu^{2+} ion. From the knowledge of p_n and the concentration of copper in the solution, it is possible to calculate the thermodynamic solubility product. The activity coefficient of copper has been calculated on the same principle as on bi-monovalent salts (this *Journal*, 1952, **29**, 169). The mean value of the solubility product of copper oxide comes out to be 1.5×10^{-20} .

The solubility product determined by us as well as by previous authors corresponds to the following equilibrium :

and not to the equilibrium

The solubility product corresponding to the two equilibria should be as follows

$$(1) K_{sp} = \exp. \frac{\mu_{\text{CuO}, n\text{H}_2\text{O}} - (n-1)\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \mu^\circ_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} - 2\mu^\circ_{\text{OH}^-}}{RT}$$

$$(2) K_{sp} = \exp. \frac{\mu_{\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2} - \mu^\circ_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} - 2\mu^\circ_{\text{OH}^-}}{RT}$$

Our value, which corresponds to the first equilibrium, is in fair agreement with those of previous authors, referred to earlier. The solubility product (2.6×10^{-19}) corresponding to the second equilibrium has been determined by Nasanen (*Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicae*, A. 597, 1942).

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